
**“AN EMPERCIAL STUDY ON DECATHLON “FLX” BATS AND ITS POTENTIAL
OPPURTUNITY IN INTERNATIONAL MARKET”**

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Abstract

In India as cricket is hugely popular game and which is played in every nook and corner, Decathlon since its start of India operation has no cricket specific brand. Decathlon sports India limited ventured out to set up a country specific brand. The company in 2014 launched a country specific brand “FLX” with lot of skepticism. The manufacturing and the sale is limited to only one specific country which is much into large scale manufacturing and selling, the idea of selling sports products to one particular country, were in the expectation of the customers were to be kept in mind while fixing the pricing, the quality and the most important the brand image to be projected without disturbing the quality and the pricing with keeping in mind the decathlon policy of “Sports for all; All for Sports”. Hence in the present study an efforts is made to determine the potential opportunity for Decathlon “FLX” bats and the acceptance level of Decathlon “FLX” bats by the customers in the country which will help the company to a large extent in understanding the acceptance level of these bats and improve based on the research findings.

1.1.Introduction

In a country like India, Decathlon since its start of India operations had no cricket specific brand. The company was definitely losing a large chunk of revenue due to this, which was mostly shared by many local and multi-national companies in the cricket segment. As there was lot of significant importance involved with the sport and after the success of the Indian Cricket team winning the 2011 world cup, Decathlon Sports India Limited ventured out to set up a country specific brand. The company in 2014 launched a country specific brand “FLX” with lot of skepticism. The manufacturing and the sale is limited to only one specific country which for Decathlon was swimming against strong currents, its own policies. The company which is much into large scale manufacturing and selling, the idea of selling sports products to one particular country, were in the expectations of the customers were to be kept in mind while fixing the pricing, the quality and the most important the brand image to be projected without disturbing the quality and the pricing with keeping in mind the Decathlon policy of “Sports for All; All for Sports”.

2 . Review of literature and Gaps

The study under taken being exploratory in nature, the research articles, journals, case studies with the relevant topic were limited when undertaking the study. With extensive research and deliberations we were able to find four related research topics related to the study.

- a. **Sustainability of Supply Chains among Sports Goods Manufacturing in India- Aniruddha Mysore Srinath (2012)** the case study was taken up by Mr. Srinath to understand the PESTAL, supply chain factors which impact the bat industry in India. The research topic takes into account the growth of cricket, the growth of the industry and the current situation of bat industry in India, the various government rules and regulation which impact the earnings and the revenue. The research explores the unhealthy nature of competition, exploitation of raw materials and the every growing demand of cricket in India which fuels it. The research derives specifics inputs from the PushpKholi of BAS Vampire cricket and other industry experts who provide their key inputs in understanding the case better.
- b. **LalitModi: The home run: IPL has turned the cricket world upside down and transformed BCCI into an 800-pound gorilla in ICC (2013)** the cover story by Mr. SharniPande brings to us the most important topic of this century, for many, The Indian Premier League. The author in its short cover story covers a lot of ground to and explains how the then chairman, Mr. LalitModi turned around the fortune for cricket in India and re-energized the love, the passion which the sport holds in this country. The outcome of mother of all marketing events, the outcome, BCCI virtually running the international council, the BCCI becoming richer by 800 pounds, a platform for youngster to showcase their talent, and most importantly livelihood for lakhs of people involved with the game. How the dwindling, declining bat industry of Kashmir was given the much needed boost to sustain.
- c. **Sports Retailing in India Opportunities, Constrains and Way forward- Arpitha Mukherjee and Co. (2010)** this paper co-authored by Mr. Mukhrjee and puts forth the new dimension of retail sector in India, sports retailing. The paper explains, the emergence of sports retailing in India, the growth of this sector, ease of doing business due to introduction of FDI by the government. The case suggests that the entire industry is still niche and with the permission to allow 51 per-cents FDI in retail which is win-win situation for both the country as well as the segment. Uplifting the ban on retail FDI will help increase the sourcing from India, will lead to diffusion of technology, proliferation of brands, will increase the investments in sports and promotion and others.
- d. **Bat-Power Rules in Modern Cricket; High-scoring World Cup proves bat-power rules one-day cricket (2015)** Lord, Richard from the Wall Street Journal, describes the overshadowing of the willow power in the current cricketing age. Gone are those days when a score of 200 plus was a herculean target. Today, likes like Chris Gayle, AbDevilers, McCullum make score of even 350 plus look like a rat chase. This is all because of the technological changes that have warranted the bats to change their shape and dimensions,

giving batsmen an edge over the bowlers. It was legendary Australian fast bowler Dennis Lille who prompted the rules to be changed to make the entire bat face made of wood rather than iron or other materials being used then. Similarly, another attempt because of technological advance, a carbon fiber-reinforced bat used by then Australian captain Ricky Ponting in 2005, was swiftly banned, as were attempts to turn the handle into a hollow plastic tube that were tried out in England at about the same time was also drained out.

The current guidelines warrants a batsman to use bats made of a tough willow main section spliced to a bamboo cane handle covered with a rubber grip. The rules about their size concern total height and the width of the face the dimensions being 38 inches (96.52 cm), and 4.25 inches (10.79 cm) respectively; but the guideline doesn't stipulate anything that a bat has to be less than a certain weight or depth

Changes in the bat dimensions and hard hitting are the main contributors to the exciting game of cricket which we witness today. The changes in the bat dimensions and rules will continue to exist, what matters is the mind-set it has created in the minds of customers which have made cricket an exciting, fun sport to look forward to.

- e. Cricket Bat Industry as an Economically Viable Livelihood Option in Kashmir: Present Status and Future Prospects- by Masoodi, T H, Ahmad, Hillal; Gangoo, S A and Sofi, P A(2014) Kashmir willow, the name is itself derived from the heaven on earth "Kashmir". The place is not only known for its scenic landscape, but also for the quality of cricket bats it produces and is more famous for the willow. The case study deals with the various facets of bat industry in Kashmir, and the economic potential it has. The study was limited to 70 units concentrated in Jammu and Kashmir area. The case explains to us the process of manufacturing, the BCR, the net income, the cost and return analysis by all size if manufacturing units, small, medium, large. The study even explains the export competitiveness, which were essentials for my study and details of the manufacturing and other costs. The end conclusion of the study was that, despite underutilization of installed capacity, the bats manufacturing units business is lucrative venture in Kashmir and can be scaled to become highly productive and can be a potential market for the world.

3. Statement of the problem

"An empirical study to determine the potential opportunity of Decathlon "FLX" in international market with the backdrop of the problem statement, we would like to determine in this study whether there is any kind of potential opportunity for Decathlon "FLX" bat in the international bat market through international Decathlon retail stores. The crucial inputs derived from the respondents and other important stake holders will be the bases of the outcome. The two most important factors which will determine the outcome are the two dimensions of the bat, Physical Dimensions like (Bat Height, Bat Weight, Bat Handle et.al) and relevant price positioning of the bats, whether the two dimensions, physical dimensions of the bat and the price range are in tune with the customer perception which will then determine the international customer outlook of the acceptance level of the brand.

5. Objectives of the study

1. The analyses the relation between price & quality with purchasing process acceptance
2. To analyze the relation between pricing & quality with demographic variables(Gender, income and occupation level of the respondents gender of the respondents

4. Scope of the project

The research scope included all the various parameters which determine the selection of the bats by a customer. The study makes an effort to understand how various demographics parameters like Age, Income, Occupation, Education level impact the overall buying behavior. When dealing with the research, it was brought to our notice that customers mindset in India, while purchasing a cricket bat is limited to the brand image, much on the referrals from acquaintances, the bats used by the poster boys of Indian cricket team and other related factors. But, what was interesting to know in the course of the study that customer knowledge of cricket bat is limited while making a choice, and are rigid while exercising the options, look for high quality in limited price. As the research in the related topic is only limited to bat manufacturing theories, the research tries to address as how customer respond to the innovations by a private label, the brand perception they have set and what are the various factors which customers look forward which make a private label successful.

Hypothesis

H₀: No co-relation exists of the "FLX" Decathlon bats against the price while bat purchasing process

H₁: Co-relation exists of the "FLX" Decathlon bats against the Price while bat purchasing process.

H₀: No co-relation exists of the "FLX" Decathlon bats against the quality while bat purchasing process

H₁: There is co-relation which exists of the "FLX" Decathlon bats against the quality while bat purchasing process.

H₀: No co-relation exists of the "FLX" Decathlon bats against the pricing and quality of FLX bats with the gender of the respondents.

H₁: There co-relation exists of the "FLX" Decathlon bats against the pricing and quality of FLX bats with the gender of the respondents.

H₀: No co-relation exists of the "FLX" Decathlon bats against the pricing and quality of FLX bats with the income level of the respondents.

H₁: There co-relation exists of the "FLX" Decathlon bats against the pricing and quality of FLX bats with the income level of the respondents.

H₀: No co-relation exists of the "FLX" Decathlon bats against the pricing and quality of FLX bats with the occupation level of the respondents.

H₁: There co-relation exists of the "FLX" Decathlon bats against the pricing and quality of FLX bats with the occupation level of the respondents.

6. Sampling of the study

Sampling Frame

As the game of cricket is played by all and many in India, the population for the sample size is huge. The project employees, simple random sampling at the first phase, were in foot-falls of the user is "FLX"- Department of Decathlon- Whitefield store are selected randomly in terms of age, gender, occupation, income level. Et.al to exercise the questionnaire. The sampling involves various age groups, starting from 6 years old to 50 and above years engaged in playing cricket at various levels. The reason for simple random sampling being, as the population under study was large, and the level of cricket played by the respondents varied, the need to extract data from different quarters of population was warranted. The age demographics was divided into equal intervals of 9 years, with many deliberations and discussions the age was set at 6 years was set and taken as the threshold level for the play of cricket. The income level set for the sample size was determined taking into various factors. The basic logic taken up for discussion in this section was that cricket is not limited to one level of income, it is a sport played by all and many, we chalked out the income bracket at the lowest level. Similarly, the occupation level of the respondents was set in relation with the income level and the education particulars. To cite an example, a customer "A" with "X" level of income and "Y" level of occupation may play leisure cricket and used a low quality bat. Similarly, a customer "B" with similar level of income and occupation may be playing professional level of cricket with a higher quality of bat. As the scope of the study was only limited to exercising the options from the foot-falls in the retail store, the need to choose random sample for the study was un-avoidable

Tools for Data Collection

The data for this study was collected from through a questionnaire, via personal interview procedure. In the entire process, we were able to meet and engage with people from various ages, occupation, income, gender, language, various walks of life in a nut shell. The entire process was interesting and the choice of personal interview for data collection helped us get deep and valuable insights which helped us analysis the key attributes and understand the customer bat selection process better. The need was warranted as the inputs derived, helped us give definite recommendations about the brand, the quality, the price and other key aspects which will help the brand take corrective actions, if any.

Data Analysis

In the questionnaire which was provided most questions put forth to the respondents were closed ended questions. The respondents had to exercise the option and rate the questions accordingly on a Likert scale provided with 5 being the highest rating and 1 being the lowest, 3 the median as neutral. The question related to demographics was based on nominal scale.

Table -1,

Classify the demographic variables of the respondent i.e. Age, Gender & Occupation of the respondents

	Age	Frequency	Percent
Valid	6yr-15yr	37	20.7
	16yr-25yr	62	34.6
	26yr-34-yr	54	30.17
	35yr-44yr	19	10.7
	45yr>	7	3.92
	Total	179	100
	Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Valid	Male	166	92.7
	Female	13	7.3
	Total	179	100
	Occupation	Frequency	Percentage
Valid	Student	66	36.87
	Service	90	50.3
	Business	7	3.91
	Freelancer	16	8.94
	Total	179	100

Table -2

Classify the respondents on the basis of education & playing level of the respondents

	Education	Frequency	Percent
Valid	Student	60	33.52
	Higher secondary	01	0.55
	Pre-University	13	7.27
	Graduate	87	48.7
	Post-graduate	18	10.05
	Total	179	100
	Playing level of respondent	Frequency	Percentage
Valid	Leisure level	82	45.81
	Intermediate level	94	52.51
	Professional level	03	1.68
	Total	179	100

Inferences

The above table depicts the respondents on the basis of the age, gender & occupation. The data reveals that majority (34.6%) of the respondents belong the age category of 16-25 years, 30.17% belong the age category of 26-34 years, 20.7% belong to the age category of 6-15 years, 10.7% belong to the age category of 35-44 years and only 3.92% belong to the age category of 45 years. The data reveals that there is dominance of male players is at highest level at 92.7 percent against that of female players at only 7.3 percent. This information will help in developing products for the same gender. The data on occupation reveals that majority of the respondents belong the service as their occupation have a larger percentage of shares at 50.3 percentages, indicating that they continue with the sport, either in leisure or professional way, followed by 36.87% of the respondents are students, 8.94% of the respondents are freelancers and only 3.91% are business class. The data reveals that majority (48.76%) of the respondents are graduates, 33.52% are students below higher schooling and 10.5% of the respondents are post graduates and only 7.27% of the respondents are pre-university students. Among the respondents only 1.68% of the respondents are professionals playing the sport and 52.51% play are intermediate level and 45.81% of the respondents play for leisure level.

3. STATISTICAL TECHNIQUES

Kaiser- Mayo- Olkin Tests- KMO Tests

The Kaiser Mayo Olkin Tests deals with measure of sample adequacy, the sample adequacy varies between the ranges of 0 to 1. The value closer to 1 is better and the value 0.6 is the minimum suggested value. The Bartlett's test of Sphericity is the test for null hypothesis to testify if the co-relation matrix has an identity matrix. These minimum standards are vital as these tests provide the minimum standard to proceed for Factor analysis. KMO and Bartlett's Test. The measure of sampling through Kaiser- Meyer- Olkin Tests

Kaiser – Meyer – Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy		0.657
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi – Square	395.916
	df	15
	Sig.	.000

Normally, $0 < KMO < 1$, If $KMO > 0.5$, the sample is adequate. Here, $KMO = 0.657$ which indicates that the sample is adequate and we may proceed with the Factor Analysis.

Bartlett's Test of Sphericity

Taking a 95% level of significance, $\alpha = 0.05$, therefore the Factor Analysis is valid therefor we reject the null hypothesis H_0 and accept the alternate hypothesis (H_1) that there may be statistically significant interrelationship between variable.

Table -3 - Communalities Quality

	Initial	Extraction
Quality Wood Quality	1.000	.609
Quality Bat Handle	1.000	.787
Quality Bat Thickness	1.000	.598
Quality Feel Grip	1.000	.569
Quality Bat Finishing	1.000	.799
Quality Bat Warranty	1.000	.781

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Table 4. Communalities- Pricing

	Initial	Extraction
Competitive Pricing Of FLX Bats	1.000	.548
Perception Satisfaction Against Bat Quality	1.000	.454
Perception Satisfaction Against Brand Image Perceived	1.000	.714
Satisfaction with price range provided	1.000	.524
Requirement Higher Price Range Bats	1.000	.754
Requirement Lower Price Range Bats	1.000	.643

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

ANOVA

One way results for Quality and Pricing co-relation of Decathlon FLX Bats

H_0 : No co-relation exists of the "FLX" Decathlon bats against the price while bat purchasing process

H₁: Co-relation exists of the "FLX" Decathlon bats against the Price while bat purchasing process.

H₀: No co-relation exists of the "FLX" Decathlon bats against the quality while bat purchasing process

H₁: There is co-relation which exists of the "FLX" Decathlon bats against the quality while bat purchasing process.

Table -4

ANOVA						
One way results for Quality and Pricing co-relation of Decathlon FLX Bats						
		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
QUALITY SUM	Between Groups	1407.211	4	351.803	22.965	.000
	Within Groups	2665.504	174	15.319		
	Total	4072.715	178			
PRICING SUM	Between Groups	4.816	4	1.204	.149	.963
	Within Groups	1402.034	174	8.058		
	Total	1406.849	178			

ANOVA						
One way results for Pricing Dimension by age of the respondents						
		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
	Between groups	404.291	4	101.073	17.542	.000
	Within groups	1002.558	174	5.762		
	Total	1406.846	178			

ANOVA						
One way results for Quality Dimension by age of the respondents						
		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
	Between groups	1469.500	4	367.375	24.556	.000
	Within groups	2603.215	174	14.961		
	Total	4072.715	178			

Inferences

a. The one way result from one way ANOVA conveys that there is an overall significance of $F=22.965(p=0.000, p<0.05)$ for the first dimension i.e. Quality and for the second dimension i.e. Pricing, the overall significance $F= 0.149 (p=0.963, p<0.05)$. Since the P level is lesser than 5% level of significance, we accept the Alternate Hypothesis and Reject the Null Hypothesis. Indicating, that the quality is the first dimension which customers look for while bat buying process.

b. The one way result from one way ANOVA conveys that there is an overall significance of $F=17.542(p=0.000, p<0.05)$ for the Price of the FLX Bats. In order to find a co-relation between the ages and whether price plays any factor in the bat selection process. In order to determine this, we make use of the post hoc test (Games- Howell Test). The test indicates that the mean difference between the respondents of the age 26 years to 34 years is higher (Mean= 6.48772) indicating that these respondents make a conclusive decision before making a bat purchase. Since the P level is lesser than 5 % level of significance; we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternate hypothesis. Thus this indicates that the age determines the price point of the bats while making a purchase.

c. The one way result from one way ANOVA conveys that there is an overall significance of $F=24.556(p=0.000, p<0.05)$ for the Quality Dimensions of the FLX Bats. In order to find a co-relation between the age and quality playing any factor in the bat selection process, In order to determine this, we make use of the post hoc test (Games- Howell Test). The test indicates that the mean difference between the respondents of the age 35 years to 44 years is higher (Mean= 11.9843) indicating that these respondents are educated, with suitable amount of income and make the best purchases in terms of the quality of the bat. The level of significance is lesser than 5% level of significance, hence the null hypothesis is rejected and alternate hypothesis is accepted. The quality plays an important factor while selecting a bat. This may be due to the experience gained while playing the game or the game demands the need for that quality of bat.

ANOVA

One way ANOVA results for pricing and quality by Gender, Income level and occupation

H_0 : No co-relation exists of the "FLX" Decathlon bats against the pricing and quality of FLX bats with the gender of the respondents.

H_1 : There co-relation exists of the "FLX" Decathlon bats against the pricing and quality of FLX bats with the gender of the respondents.

H_0 : No co-relation exists of the "FLX" Decathlon bats against the pricing and quality of FLX bats with the income level of the respondents.

H_1 : There co-relation exists of the "FLX" Decathlon bats against the pricing and quality of FLX bats with the income level of the respondents.

H_0 : No co-relation exists of the "FLX" Decathlon bats against the pricing and quality of FLX bats with the occupation level of the respondents.

H_1 : There co-relation exists of the "FLX" Decathlon bats against the pricing and quality of FLX bats with the occupation level of the respondents.

Table -5

ANOVA						
One way ANOVA results for pricing and quality and gender of the respondents.						
		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
QUALITY SUM	Between Groups	124.111	1	124.111	5.563	.019
	Within Groups	3948.604	177	22.308		
	Total	4072.715	178			
PRICING SUM	Between Groups	23.579	1	23.579	3.017	.084
	Within Groups	1383.270	177	7.815		
	Total	1406.849	178			
ANOVA						
One way ANOVA results for pricing and quality and Income Level of the respondents.						
		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
QUALITY SUM	Between Groups	840.102	4	210.025	11.305	.000
	Within Groups	3232.613	174	18.578		
	Total	4072.715	178			
PRICING SUM	Between Groups	256.300	4	210.025	11.305	.000
	Within Groups	1150.549	174	6.612		
	Total	1406.849	178			
ANOVA						
One way ANOVA results for pricing and quality and Occupation Level of the respondents.						
		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
QUALITY SUM	Between Groups	803.310	3	267.770	14.333	.000
	Within Groups	3269.405	175	18.682		
	Total	4072.715	178			
PRICING SUM	Between Groups	89.167	3	29.722	3.947	.009
	Within Groups	1317.682	175	7.530		
	Total	1406.849	178			

Inference

a. The one way result from one way ANOVA conveys that there is an overall significance of $F=5.563(p=0.000, p<0.05)$ for price and quality and the gender of the respondents. The Alternate Hypothesis is accepted at 5% level of significance. With 5% level of significance and the value of P being lower, we accept the alternate hypothesis and reject the null hypothesis. Indicating that gender of the respondents plays an important role while making the bat choice.

b. The one way result from one way ANOVA conveys that there is an overall significance of $F=11.305 (p<0.05)$ for the Quality Dimensions of the FLX Bats and the overall significance

of $F = 0.084$ ($p=0.000$, $p<0.05$.) The Alternate Hypothesis is accepted at 5% level of significance. With 5% level of significance and the value of P being lower, we accept the alternate hypothesis and reject the null hypothesis. Indicating that income level of the respondents plays an important level while making the bat choice, people with higher income may go for a higher price bats and vice-versa.

c. The one way result from one way ANOVA convey that there is an overall significance of $F=14.333$ ($p=0.000$, $p<0.05$) for the Quality Dimensions of the FLX Bats and the overall significance of $F = 3.947$ ($p=0.000$, $p<0.05$). Since the level of P is lesser than 5% level of significance; we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternate hypothesis. The occupation level, which is one of the demographics, determines the bat selection process.

Table 6: Co-Relation Coefficient Factors between the Quality Sum and the Pricing of FLX Decathlon Bats.

		QUALITY SUM	PRICING SUM
QUALITY SUM	Pearson Correlation	1	.647**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	179	179
PRICING SUM	Pearson Correlation	.647**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	179	179

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Interpretation

The correlations of two factors (factors preferred by the customers while making a bat selection) i.e. The Pricing of the FLX bats and the Quality of FLX bats. The Pearson Correlation at .647t indicates that customer look for better quality of the bat, for the price they have provided for. These two dimensions will help make "FLX" a better brand by giving a better quality for affordable pricing as per the customer perception.

Regression Analysis

Table -7

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the estimate
1	.309 ^a	.095	.085	.48156

a. Predictors: (Constant), QUALITY SUM, PRICING SUM

Table 8

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	4.304	2	2.152	9.279	.000 ^b
	Residual	40.814	176	.232		
	Total	45.117	178			

a. Dependent Variable: Will you recomend FLX to aqisstances

b. Predictors: (Constant), QUALITY SUM, PRICING SUM

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.595	.205		12.663	.000
	PRICING SUM	.034	.017	.190	2.023	.045
	QUALITY SUM	-.042	.010	-.396	-4.209	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Will you recommend FLX to quittances

In order to check whether the customer will accept “FLX” bats against the pricing and quality dimension provided. The hypothesis is check through multiple regression analysis. The dependent variable taken for this study is the pricing and quality dimension with the independent variable being the “customer’s recommendation of FLX bats to their acquaintance’s”.

In the analysis of various table (ANOVA) we test that null hypothesis, i.e. there is no impact of the independent variable on the dependent variable against the alternate hypothesis, i.e. the two dimensions pricing of FLXB bats and the quality of FLXB Bats doesn’t affect the recommendation of the FLX bats to the acquaintances and does the pricing and quality of the bats meets international bat standards. The P value from the ANOVA table is 0.000 which is less than the significance value of 0.05 and this leads us to fail to accept the null hypothesis, in other words we accept the alternative hypothesis and say that there is a significant impact of the pricing and quality of the bats on the recommendation level the adjusted R^2 is 0.085. This means that the regression analysis can explain 8.5% of the data. The P value 0.000 < significant value of 0.05 and thus we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternate hypothesis which in this case is as below

Hypothesis Accepted- The two dimensions i.e. pricing and quality of the bats have definitive impact on customers while the bat selection process.

Findings, Recommendations and Conclusion

1. There were considerable amount of respondents in the age bracket of 6 years to 15 years indicating that the parents are willing to send their kids to cricketing academy. There is a growing awareness of the sport in the country and younger generation takes this sport in a sporting spirit and male were on a considerable higher side which indicates that male population dominate this sport.
2. Most important, when asked about brand recall about “FLX”, most of the customers were not really aware about the brand. This is a the most important find from marketing point of view, the company has to put in more efforts in increasing the brand recall amongst the customer.
3. The customers were not aware of “FLX” brand by Decathlon, until they visited the store. This again from marketing perspective is most important and making the brand more aware in the minds of the customer.

4. The customers who visited the store, maximum respondents had never used "FLX" bats and this was their first purchase. The company needs to maximize customer interaction at this level so as to gain maximum inputs and pushing the brand amongst the customer peer groups and acquaintances.
5. The customers when compared the price range of the "FLX" bats in Decathlon store. The response for this was neutral indicating that the price for the bat provided was meeting customers' perception about price. Decathlon, can bring about certain changes in the price range, by increasing the depth and width of the price range.
6. The plus point about "FLX" from the customers was about the bat warranty provided which is 6 months conditionally and 2 years conditionally warranty, which some bat manufacturers don't provide.
7. The customers were a little skeptical about recommending the bats to their friends or acquaintances. Little is known on this front, needs more in depth research to find out the reasons.

Recommendations

1. The company needs to increase the brand awareness of "FLX" bats and not limit itself to world of mouth publicity.
2. The company needs to build customer engagement programs to derive inputs from the customers and make the brand better.
3. Customer engagement programs can be indoor cricket tournaments on regular basis, sponsoring local cricket tournaments et.al
4. The company needs to put more efforts on marketing aspect of the product. Some low cost methods may be banners or hoardings in the store.
5. The company has to provide the brand with more visual space in the store premises and make the area more visible and attractive to its customers.
6. Making the customer feel good about the brand, in tune with an international brand they perceive.

Conclusion

FLX as a brand has carved out and marked a niche segment of its own in the cricket bat segment. The brand is showing a positive growth in terms of its sales, the level of customer acceptance in such a short span of time. With the international experience and expertise of Decathlon in sports retail sector, the brand is growing in a positive direction. As cricket is a hugely popular game in India and played in every nook and corner, the company now needs to connect with more of these grass roots players in understanding their needs and demands and going beyond the quintessential retail working scenario and build the brand. By the views of the respondents "FLX" as a brand will be a hit in international market which has just accepted cricket as a sport, countries like Hong Kong, Netherlands etc. The company needs to first engage in brand building in countries where other brand manufacturing companies have already chalked out their market. To conclude, I strongly feel that "FLX" can be marketed internationally and will be a cash cow for Decathlon if nurtured well.

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